

Results of Determining the Level of Influence of Geno-Modified Soy on the Normal Intestinal Microflora of Laboratory Animals

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In addition to various microorganisms that enter the body from the external environment, there are also microorganisms that live in symbiosis with the human body and make up the normal human microflora. They are located in different biotopes and are important for the functioning of the body. One of these biotopes is the large intestine, the standard microflora of which, consisting of indigenous and facultative microorganisms, is of great importance for life. It is known that the microbiocenosis of the large intestine consists of more than 450 microorganisms and participates in the metabolism of the "host" of the body and the formation of colonization resistance in the intestine.

Under the influence of various external and internal factors, the disruption of the normal microflora of the large intestine is characterized by a qualitative and quantitative imbalance of indigenous and facultative microflora and is called intestinal dysbacteriosis. Factors leading to intestinal dysbacteriosis include many physical, chemical and biological factors.

Today, many scientific works have been conducted on the various effects of genetically modified (GM) products on the human body, and the opinions of specialists on this matter differ. There are scientific works confirming the following provisions, which note the negative effect of GM products on the immune system, liver and pancreas, thymus and spleen, as well as hematological and biochemical changes, mutagen and negative impact on reproductive activity and bone marrow. cells have been proven.

An analysis of many scientific literature sources shows that studies of the level of impact of GM products on the microbiocenosis of human biotopes, including the microbiosis of the colon, are few and scattered.

Taking into account the above, **the aim of the study** was to determine the level of influence of GM soy on the microbiocenosis of the colon of purebred rats.

Material and methods. For this purpose, a total of 90 male white rats were included in the study, which were divided into 3 groups: Group 1 - intact white rats on a standard vivarium diet, not receiving GM and non-GM soy (n=30); Group 2 - non-white rats (n=30) receiving non-GM soy on a standard vivarium diet; Group 3 - white mongrel rats (n=30) receiving GM soy on a standard vivarium diet.

These groups were representative and differed in only one characteristic. Particular attention was paid to whether the studies were randomized and whether they complied with the principles of evidence-based medicine. The study strictly followed the ethical principles of working with laboratory animals and the rules of biological safety.

After delivery of the large intestinal mass of white rats to the bacteriological laboratory, bacteriological studies were carried out on the appropriate nutrient media (Blaurock, CPM-4 (MPC-4), Endo, Sabouraud, egg-yolk agar, etc.) according to the "Bergey Manual of Systematic Bacteriology" (1997) microorganisms were identified and differentiated: *Bifidobacterium spp*, *Lactobacillus spp*, *Escherichia coli*, *Enterobacter species*, *Proteus species*, *Staphylococcus species*, *Streptococcus species*, *Candida species*. *Intergenerational and interspecies identification was carried out using nutrient media from HiMedia (India).*

The results were analyzed using traditional methods of variation statistics; the principles of evidence-based medicine were observed during the organization and conduct of the research.

Results and discussion. The obtained results showed that there are convincing differences between the compared groups in the studied quantitative indicators (Table 1).

Table 1 Comparative analysis of quantitative indicators of the colon microbiocenosis in non-GM soy and intact laboratory animals, lg KXQB/ml (M±m).

Microorganisms	Group 1, n=30	Group 2, n=30
Bifidobacteria	5.10±0.2	4.00±0.1* ↓
types lactobacilli	6.10±0.2	4.00±0.1* ↓
Escherichia coli (lactose positive)	5.15±0.2	5.00±0.2 ↔
Escherichia coli (lactose negative)	0	0 ↔
Enterobacteria	1.20±0.1	5.00±0.2* ↑
Proteus view	0.80±0.1	5.00±0.2* ↑
Staphylococcus	4.10±0.1	5.00±0.2* ↑
Streptococcus spp.	6.30±0.3	4.00±0.2* ↓
Candida	3.60±0.1	7.00±0.1* ↑

Note: * - sign of reliable difference between groups; ↑, ↓ – direction of changes; ↔ – no reliable difference.

It is evident that 7 out of 9 examined representatives of the large intestinal microflora (77.78%) showed convincing changes, it is also worth noting that the quantitative indices of microorganisms changed in different directions compared to the norm (Group 1). Only the parameters related to *Escherichia coli* did not change significantly in both groups. Non-pathogenic *Escherichia coli* (lactose-positive *Escherichia coli*), forming fuchsin-red (or colorless) colonies with a metallic sheen on Endo medium, breaking down lactose into acid and gas in the Hiss series, forming light red (or colorless) colonies with a dark center on Endo medium, breaking down lactose in the Hiss series. Quantitative *Escherichia coli* (lactose-negative *Escherichia coli*), lacking the ability to break down and showing pathogenicity, the indices were close to each other ($P>0.05$).

The analysis showed that in the 2nd group (consuming non-GM soy), compared to the control group (intact), there was a convincing decrease in the quantitative indicators of the representatives of the normal indigenous microflora of the large intestine. The quantitative decrease in *Bifidobacterium spp* was up to 1.28 times ($R<0.05$), and the quantitative decrease in *Lactobacillus spp* was up to 1.53 times ($R<0.05$). It was shown that this condition is the first sign of dysbiotic conditions in the large intestine of laboratory animals of the 2nd group.

Streptococcus spp, another representative of normal microflora, the concentration of which in the large intestine decreases by 1.58 times ($R<0.05$). This condition was also interpreted as a prelude to dysbiotic processes. Considering that in the 2nd group there was only one external agent (shadow), unlike the control group, these changes were due to its influence, and the decrease in the quantitative indicators of the indigenous intestinal microflora was interpreted as a temporary condition, since it was an unfamiliar product for the body of non-white rats.

When comparing the indicators of the control group with laboratory animals, it should be noted that the quantitative increase in the group indicators mainly accounted for enterobacteria and coagulase-positive cocci, taking into account their entry into the facultative (transient) microflora of animals. large intestine, as well as the fact that they make their pathogenicity invisible when entering favorable conditions, an imbalance was observed in the aboriginal and facultative microorganisms in this biotope compared to each other. Thus, in the 2nd group, a quantitative increase was observed in *Enterobacter spp* and *Proteus spp*, representatives of the Enterobacteriaceae family - by 4.17 times ($R<0.001$) and

6.25 times ($R < 0.001$), respectively. The quantitative increase in these microorganisms was assessed as the onset of dysbacteriosis processes in the large intestine.

A similar result, but with less intensity, was observed for *Staphylococcus spp*. It should also be noted that the intensity of the tendency of this microorganism to decrease in numbers was less than that of gram-negative bacteria. The difference between the control group and the comparison group was 1.58 times in favor of intact animals ($R < 0.05$).

Thus, in the normal microflora of the large intestine of white rats fed a standard vivarium diet without GM soy, various quantitative differences were found compared to intact laboratory animals; quantitative changes of different directions were detected in 7 of 9 representatives of the normal microflora (77.78%) ($R < 0.05$). The main convincing differences were observed for *the species Bifidobacterium* (a decrease of 1.28 times), *Lactobacillus spp* (a decrease of 1.53 times), *Enterobacter spp* and *Proteus spp* (an increase of 4.16 and 6.25 times). Such imbalances between the indigenous and facultative microflora of the large intestine are the initial signs of dysbiosis processes and do not indicate the development of complete dysbacteriosis, since *no intergroup differences were found in pathogenic and non-pathogenic strains of Escherichia coli. one of the main microorganisms of the intestinal microflora*, and lactose-negative strains did not germinate. The reason for the quantitative changes was the use of soy, and the main reason was that it was unfamiliar to the animal organism.

At the next stage of the scientific work, quantitative indices of the colon microbiocenosis of purebred white rats with the addition of GM soy to the standard vivarium diet were studied and the obtained figures were analyzed. Intact (not receiving GM soy) laboratory animals were used for comparison. All results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Comparative analysis of quantitative indicators of the colon microbiocenosis of GM soybean and intact laboratory animals, lg KXQB/ml (M±m).

Microorganisms	Group 1, n=30	Group 3, n=30
Bifidobacteria	5.10±0.2	2.10±0.1* ↓
types lactobacilli	6.10±0.2	2.00±0.2* ↓
Escherichia coli (lactose positive)	5.15±0.2	0 ↓
Escherichia coli (lactose negative)	0	5.30±0.3* ↑
Enterobacteria	1.20±0.1	5.45±0.2* ↑
Proteus	0.80±0.1	3.00±0.1* ↑
Staphylococcus	4.10±0.1	6.15±0.2* ↑
Streptococcus spp.	6.30±0.3	4.30±0.2* ↓
Candida	3.60±0.1	7.00±0.4* ↑

Note: * - sign of reliable difference between groups; ↑, ↓ – direction of changes; ↔ – no reliable difference.

When analyzing the quantitative indicators of microorganisms that make up the microflora of the large intestine in Table 2, it was found that they all had intergroup differences. These differences were observed for all 9 microorganisms studied.

The most profound quantitative changes were observed in representatives of the normal indigenous microflora of the large intestine - *Bifidobacterium spp*. A similar result was obtained for *Lactobacillus spp* - *the tendency and intensity of the decrease in quantitative indicators was the same as for bifidobacteria, the quantitative decrease was on average 3.05 times (R < 0.001)*.

Compared with the control group (intact), it was found that in the main group (fed with GM soybeans), the number of representatives of the native microflora decreased by 2.43-3.05 times, which is the beginning of dysbiotic processes in this biotope. It was confirmed that these quantitative changes are

the effect of an external factor on native microorganisms, if we take into account that only GM soybeans suffered from them as an external factor, then it is clear that the results obtained are its effect.

We observed a different picture when studying the quantitative indicator of *E. coli*, another representative of the normal microflora of the large intestine. These non-pathogenic gram-negative bacteria, capable of breaking down lactose, grew in the amount of 5.15 ± 0.2 lg KXQB/ml in the control group, but did not grow in the biological material taken from the large intestine of white rats. belonging to group 3. However, pathogenic strains of *Escherichia coli* were detected in the amount of 5.30 ± 0.3 lg KXQB/ml, and it was recognized that these strains were not detected at all in the control group. This situation is one of the main signs of the process of dysbacteriosis developing in this biotope.

Other representatives of the *Enterobacteriaceae* family *Enterobacter spp* and *Proteus spp* showed changes in quantitative indicators, as well as in lactose-negative *Escherichia coli*, i.e. their quantitative indicators were higher than normal - 5.45 ± 0.2 lg KXQB/ml and 3.00 ± 0.1 lg KXQB/ml, respectively. These figures were characterized by exceeding the normal limits by 4.54 and 3.75 times ($R < 0.001$). This situation was caused by a quantitative decrease in indigenous microorganisms and an increase in opportunistic enterobacteria. Such an observed appearance is a sign of the formation of dysbiotic processes in the large intestine.

The above-mentioned sharp changes in gram-negative bacteria were not observed in gram-positive cocci, although the quantitative indicators differed between the groups, the intensity of changes was low. If in the 3rd group, compared with the 1st group, *Staphylococcus spp* was significantly increased by 1.50 times (6.15 ± 0.2 lg KXQB/ml versus 4.10 ± 0.1 lg KXQB/ml, respectively, $R < 0.05$), then the opposite picture was observed for *Streptococcus . spp*, i.e., group 3 showed significantly higher indicators than the control group (group 1). It is recognized that it decreased by 1.47 times ($R < 0.05$).

Similar results were obtained for *Candida spp*. The number of microorganisms belonging to this genus of yeast fungi in the large intestine of white rats fed GM soy was significantly higher than in intact rats that did not receive GM soy (1.94 times, $R < 0.001$).

Analysis of the obtained results showed that at the end of the observation period, laboratory animals consuming GM soy showed symptoms of colon dysbacteriosis. This condition manifests itself in:

In animals fed GM soy, compared to intact rats, the quantitative index of the native flora *Bifidobacterium spp* and *Lactobacillus spp*, representatives of the normal microflora of the large intestine, was significantly reduced by 2.43 and 3.05 times. A decrease in this quantity is an external factor that negatively affects them, and in this experiment it was interpreted as GM soy. This condition was interpreted as the first element of dysbacteriosis formed in the biotope of the large intestine.

Secondly, in non-white rats fed GM soy, unlike intact animals, lactose-negative *Escherichia coli* did not germinate (intact animals did not germinate), respectively, lactose- positive *Escherichia coli* did not germinate, and in intact animals the opposite was observed. The second element of colon dysbiosis was the germination of lactose-negative strains and the absence of detection of lactose-positive strains.

Thirdly, in laboratory animals of the 3rd group, an increase in the content of opportunistic representatives of the *Enterobacteriaceae* family *Enterobacter spp* and *Proteus spp* was found by 4.54 and 3.75 times, respectively, compared with the control group. the main cause of the imbalance of microorganisms, which is the third element of dysbacteriosis of the colon. proved.

Fourthly, although in 1-3 elements of colon dysbiosis signs of this condition were clearly manifested, no sharp changes in the indices of gram-positive cocci in this biotope were observed, and non-pathogenic *Streptococcus species*, representing the aboriginal microflora, significantly decreased by 1.47 times compared with intact laboratory animals of the main group, while coagulase-positive ones, representing the facultative microflora, and the quantitative index of *Staphylococcus spp* convincingly

increased by up to 1.50 times. Such an intergroup discrepancy was interpreted as the fourth element of colon dysbiosis.

Fifth, the quantitative determination of *Candida spp*, a representative of the facultative microflora of the large intestine, significantly increased by 1.94 times in white rats that received GM soy (group 3) compared to those that did not receive this product (group 1), as the fifth element of colon dysbacteriosis.

After the formation and development of dysbiotic processes in the large intestine of colored rats as a result of exposure to GM soy, it was necessary to assess the level of change in the quantitative indicators of indigenous and facultative microflora. For this purpose, the ratio of quantitative indicators of the compared groups to each other was studied. In the 3rd group (fed GM soy), the quantitative indicator of indigenous microorganisms was significantly reduced ($R < 0.001$) compared to the 1st group (not fed GM soy), while the quantitative indicators of facultative microorganisms were significantly increased ($R < 0.05$ - $R < 0.001$). This situation was interpreted as another indicator of the development of deep dysbacteriosis of the large intestine under the influence of GM soy.

The next stage of the research was a comparative study of the quantitative indices of the indigenous and facultative microflora of the large intestine of laboratory animals fed non-GM soybeans (Group 2) and GM soybeans (Group 3) with a standard vivarium diet. The results obtained are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Comparative analysis of quantitative indicators of the colon microbiocenosis of laboratory animals fed non-GM and GM soy, lg KXQB/ml (M±m).

Microorganisms	Group 2, n=30	Group 3, n=30
Bifidobacteria	4.00±0.1	2.10±0.1* ↓
types lactobacilli	4.00±0.1	2.00±0.2* ↓
Escherichia coli (lactose positive)	5.00±0.2	0 ↓
Escherichia coli (lactose negative)	0	5.30±0.3* ↑
Enterobacteria	5.00±0.2	5.45±0.2* ↑
Proteus view	5.00±0.2	3.00±0.1* ↑
Staphylococcus	5.00±0.2	6.15±0.2* ↑
Streptococcus spp.	4.00±0.2	4.30±0.2* ↓
Candida	7.00±0.1	7.00±0.4* ↑

Note: * - sign of reliable difference between groups; ↑, ↓ – direction of changes; ↔ – no reliable difference.

Although the results of both groups differed from those of intact laboratory animals, the intensity and depth of the changes were evident in Group 3. However, it was important to determine the extent of the difference between non-GM soy and GM soy.

Bifidobacterium spp and *Lactobacillus spp*, representatives of the indigenous microflora of the large intestine, were significantly reduced by 1.90 times and 2.0 times, respectively ($R < 0.001$).

In 2 of the 9 studied microorganisms (*Staphylococcus spp*, *Candida spp*), no intergroup differences were found ($R > 0.05$), they were quantitatively close to each other. It is noteworthy that one of them belongs to the group of facultative microorganisms. In this case, there is no known pattern. But in group 3, the aboriginal microorganisms (*Bifidobacterium spp*, *Lactobacillus spp*) decreased even more, and the facultative microorganisms (*Enterobacter spp*, *Staphylococcus spp*) increased even more. The results obtained for lactose-negative and lactose-positive *Escherichia coli* showed a sharp difference between these groups. In other words, all 5 elements of dysbacteriosis were present in laboratory animals fed with GM soy, but not in rats fed with non-GM soy.

To summarize all the results obtained, we considered it necessary to compare the indicators of all three groups (Table 4).

In this table 4, a convincing difference between the groups is clearly visible, the analyzed figures showed that in laboratory animals that were not given non-GM soy (intact, control), there were practically no changes in the normal microflora of the large intestine, and no changes in the normal microflora of the large intestine were observed. signs of dysbacteriosis were revealed; In laboratory animals fed non-GM soy (group 2), signs of dysbacteriosis were observed, the balance between indigenous and facultative microorganisms was partially disturbed, but did not form or develop; In animals receiving GM soy (group 3), the balance of indigenous and facultative microorganisms was disturbed, signs of dysbiosis were clearly observed, all 5 of its elements were identified, total dysbacteriosis of the large intestine developed. This situation was interpreted as the effect of GM soy on the body of non-white rats. It has been proven that GM soy has a negative impact on the normal microflora of the large intestine of laboratory animals, causing total dysbacteriosis.

Table 4 Quantitative state of the microflora of the colon of non-white rats on GM and non-GM diets, lg (M±m) (KXQB/ml)

Microorganisms	Group 1, n=30	Group 2, n=30	Group 3, n=30
<i>Bifidobacteria</i>	5.10±0.2	4.00±0.1	2.10±0.1*^↓
types of <i>lactobacilli</i>	6.10±0.2	4.00±0.1	2.00±0.2*^↓
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (lactose positive)	5.15±0.2	5.00±0.2	0 ↓
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (lactose negative)	0	0	5.30±0.3*↑
<i>Enterobacteria</i>	1.20±0.1	5.00±0.2	5.45±0.2*^↑
<i>Proteus</i>	0.80±0.1	5.00±0.2	3.00±0.1*^↑
<i>Staphylococcus</i>	4.10±0.1	5.00±0.2	6.15±0.2*^↑
<i>Streptococcus spp.</i>	6.30±0.3	4.00±0.2	4.30±0.2*↓
<i>Candida</i>	3.60±0.1	7.00±0.1	7.00±0.4*↑

Note: * - sign of reliable difference between groups 1 and 3; ^ - sign of convincing difference between groups 2 and 3; ↑, ↓ - directions of changes; ↔ - no reliable difference.

In order to determine the state of normal microflora of the large intestine, the level of development of dysbacteriosis, the manifestation of its depth, as a result of many studies, criteria for assessing dysbacteriosis have been created and presented to practical health care. Among these methods, we chose the one that we considered the most suitable and used it to assess dysbiosis.

This method was developed by Uzbek researchers Garib F.Yu., Adilov Sh.K. and Narbaeva I.E. Since 1995, changes in the microflora of the large intestine have been assessed at 2 levels:

In the case of first-degree dysbiosis, changes are observed only in representatives of the aboriginal group, the number of *Bifidobacterium spp* and *Lactobacillus spp* decreases compared to lactose-positive *Escherichia coli* , and intestinal dysfunction does not occur.

In stage II dysbacteriosis, as the number of indigenous microorganisms decreases, the number of facultative opportunistic microorganisms increases, the balance between them is disrupted, and signs of intestinal dysfunction appear. These levels are determined using the dysbacteriosis index (DI):

DI I = *E.coli* KXQB/g / Local microorganisms, KXQB/g <0.1;

DI II = Facultative microorganisms, KXQB/g / Local microorganisms, KXQB/g ≤ 0.5.

If DI I > 0.1; CI If I I ≤ 0.5 b , then this is grade I dysbacteriosis, if DI II > 0.5, then this is grade II dysbacteriosis, regardless of what DI I is.

The results obtained from our study were as follows:

In group 1 - $0.31 < 0.1$ (CI I); $0.37 < 0.5$ (CI II);

In the 2nd group - $0.38 < 0.1$ (CI I); $0.77 < 0.5$ (CI II);

in the 3rd group - $1.29 < 0.1$ (CI I); $3.56 < 0.5$ (CI II).

The obtained results fully confirmed the above provisions: intact laboratory animals (Group 1) showed no signs of dysbacteriosis, animals fed non-GM soy (Group 2) showed weak signs of dysbacteriosis (grade 1), and white rats fed GM soy showed signs of dysbiosis (grade 2).

Conclusions.

1. Reliable quantitative differences in the normal microflora of the large intestine of white rats fed non-GM soy compared to intact laboratory animals for *Bifidobacterium spp* (1.28-fold decrease), *Lactobacillus spp* (1.53-fold decrease), *Enterobacter spp* and *Proteus. spp* (4.16- and 6.25-fold increase). These are the initial signs of dysbacteriosis and do not indicate the development of complete dysbacteriosis, since no intergroup differences were found for lactose-negative and lactose-positive strains of *Escherichia coli*.
2. The amount of *Bifidobacterium spp* and *Lactobacillus spp* in laboratory animals fed GM soybeans was significantly reduced by 2.43 and 3.05 times compared to intact rats. This reduction was interpreted as an external factor that had a negative effect on them, and in this experiment it was GM soybeans. This condition was interpreted as the first element of dysbacteriosis formed in the colon biotope.
3. *Escherichia coli*, lactose-positive *Escherichia coli* did not germinate, unlike intact ones, in white rats fed GM soy, in intact ones the opposite occurred. The second element of colon dysbiosis was the germination of lactose-negative strains, the absence of lactose-positive strains.
4. *Enterobacter spp* and *Proteus spp* were 4.54 and 3.75 times higher, respectively, in laboratory animals fed GM soy compared to the control group, which turned out to be the third element of colon dysbacteriosis.
5. In elements 1-3 of colon dysbacteriosis, with obvious symptoms of this condition, no sharp changes in the indices of gram-positive cocci were detected - *Streptococcus spp* was significantly reduced by 1.47 times in the main group compared to the intact group. laboratory animals, and the quantitative index of coagulase-positive *Staphylococcus spp* significantly decreased by 1.50 times and increased. Such an intergroup discrepancy was interpreted as the fourth element of colon dysbiosis.
6. It has been shown that the quantitative indicator of *Candida spp* is the fifth element of colon dysbacteriosis in colored rats fed GM soy, compared with rats that did not receive this product.
7. All 5 dysbiosis elements were present in laboratory animals fed GM soy, but not in rats fed non-GM soy.
8. Determination of the dysbacteriosis index indicating levels I and II of dysbacteriosis gave the following results: in group 1 - $0.31 < 0.1$ (CI I); $0.37 < 0.5$ (CI II); in group 2 - $0.38 < 0.1$ (CI I); $0.77 < 0.5$ (CI II); in group 3 - $1.29 < 0.1$ (CI I); $3.56 < 0.5$ (CI II). Intact laboratory animals showed no signs of dysbacteriosis, signs of dysbacteriosis were weakly developed in animals fed non-GM soy (level I), and signs of dysbacteriosis were clearly evident in animals fed GM soy (level II).

LIST OF USED LINKS

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